

Assessment of Water Pollution of River Ganga by Tannery Effluent Using Fish as a Bio-Indicator in Kanpur, India

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Abstract

Kanpur City has become a large industrial complex with nearly 800 industries. It has increased the social and economic status of the city, but these industries are also causing severe environmental pollution. In addition to smoke, dust and pollutant gases, water pollution through the discharge of industrial effluents is causing severe problems. Heavy metals, such as mercury, cadmium, copper, lead and zinc are of the most important pollutants which affect aquatic environment and fish. They are extremely dangerous for the health of fish.

Most of these metals are characterized by being accumulated in tissues, and lead to the poisoning of fish. These metals can effectively influence the vital operations and reproduction of fish; weaken the immune system, and induce pathological changes. As such, fish are used as bio-indicators, playing an important role in monitoring heavy metals pollution. Finally, some recommendations are given to treatment of different kinds of wastewaters, sewage and agricultural wastes before discharge into the aquatic systems. Water pollution due to rapid industrialization and anthropogenic activities adversely affected aquatic organisms, especially fish. Here, we assessed waste water pollutant of tannery effluents in fresh water fish, an inhabitant of river Ganga. Various studies have been conducted in the past on the fresh water related to the various aspects of limnology, physico-chemistry, primary productivity, plankton etc. in relation to environmental conditions and ecology, flora and fauna of River Ganga.

Key Words : Heavy metals, Ganga River, fish, water pollution